

13 March Shock time

Expresses itself in postponing the start of the semester in the hope of being able to play for time. Further measures regarding online teaching are not tackled at first. At HHU, the phase may have been relatively short.

25 March First plans

Increased enquiries about video conferencing systems and exploring the opportunities. During tests with teachers in mid-March 2020, the existing video conferencing solutions collapsed under the increased load.

02 April Acceptance

Lecturers realised that the pandemic will not disappear within a week. ZIM stabilises the platforms by upscaling and outscaling the systems, especially VPN, network connection, ILIAS, HHU Mediathek. Selection of Webex as video conferencing solution without major discussion (expert decision)

15 April Adaptation

Lecturers' behaviour only changes on the basis of the stabilised systems. They are converting teaching to online. Tutorials and information services (Wiki) are made available relatively quickly or, for example, the interdepartmental e-learning consultation hour is set up.

Adaptation and Latency in Times of Crisis

B. Zulauf, N. Knipprath, T. Koch, E. Reidt

Changes in IT in Higher Education

17 July Hope

For a quick return to the status quo, teachers act very pragmatically across the board, adapt their teaching quickly (or not). Less conceptual, didactic-structural adaptation of teaching, but rather emergency remote teaching.

20 May Plateau

Training by a contracted service provider takes place on Webex. Committed lecturers are increasingly developing interesting teaching-learning formats with a mix of tools. The exchange in the communities and the networking at the peer level are rapidly gaining momentum.

25 September Resignation

Lecturers come to terms with the fact that the COVID19 situation will last longer. Due to the need for planning security for the semester, lecturers now prefer online teaching to heavily restricted face-to-face or hybrid teaching.

LMS ILIAS

- Eightfold increase in traffic
- Peak of 8,000 parallel sessions
- Access levelled off 3,000 - 5,000
- Optimised caching in Sept 20
- Newly installed cluster in Nov 20
- Optimised load balancing
- Spawning of processes
- Managing of ports

HHU Mediathek

Video platform performance indicators

9 October Development

The rudimentary concepts of emergency remote teaching from the summer semester are overhauled and now also conceptually adapted - also on the basis of the practical experiences from the summer semester. The very high effort for hybrid teaching is greatly underestimated.

The spectrum of lecturers diverges widely between those who would rather roll back all changes and those who would like to perpetuate e-learning opportunities on the basis of the experience gained.

Winter term Future